

Intangible characteristics of materials in industrial design

Elvin Karana, e.karana@io.tudelft.nl, Industrial Design Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Landbergstraat 15, 2628 CE, Delft, the Netherlands

Abstract

Materials, with their various physical aspects, have always covered an important role in industrial design. The competitive market rising from the increase in product consumption made industrial designers consider more about the other aspects in their materials selections, as well as the physical ones. The two crucial questions for this study stem from this point: What kinds of aspects of materials are significant for industrial designers in their selections? And what kind of data on materials do they need throughout their materials selection processes?

Throughout this study, two other aspects of materials will be mentioned: sensorial properties and the intangible characteristics. The emphasis will be on the *intangible characteristics of materials* (ICM). How we perceive a material, what kinds of associations it evokes and how we feel about it, represent the definition of the ICM for this study. Industrial designers benefit from the ICM in order to embody their intentions about the meanings of their products with the appropriate selections; and they make use of other properties of materials, like sensorial ones, as means for creating the ICM. For instance, for attributing the meaning of 'modern' (which is a term expressing an intangible characteristic) to a material, they prefer to select a material providing a grey, shiny and smooth surface (which are three features representing the sensorial properties of materials).

The objective of this paper is to emphasize the role of the intangible characteristics of materials for industrial designers. For this aim, I first evaluate how these characteristics of materials are defined in related literature and what sorts of researches have been done on this topic. Then, in the second section, I discuss a part from the findings of a field study, which was conducted with 20 industrial designers, focusing on their expectations from a materials selection source. The findings were analyzed and converted to a 'content of needed data' table.

The findings of the field study confirm that designers can easily access the technical data about the materials. However, for the pre-selection process, they do not use only technical data. On the contrary, the technical data comes third in list which consists of designers' priorities while searching for a material.

Keywords: materials, materials selection, industrial design, intangible characteristics, sensorial properties

1 Introduction

People interact with materials via products, and unaffiliated from the other parameters of design- like form, function and use- materials can be utilized by industrial designers for setting up the proposed meanings for the objected consumer groups. There are plenty of examples that provide sufficient proof for this statement. For instance, metal appears cold and can connote precision, and it seems durable and robust, and for this reason, designers can use metal to emphasize the technological superiority and high level engineering (Arabe, 2004).

Materials have been extensively studied in science and engineering for years. Existing materials selection sources can serve a useful function in giving up to date information on the technical (physical, quantifiable) aspects of materials. However, designers use also some other aspects of materials, which are intangible and non- quantifiable, in order to express their intentions through the selected materials. Conversely, even though these intangible issues in materials selection process are crucial for industrial designers, the existing materials selection sources neither consider them, nor offer a systematic way particularly for materials selection in industrial design.

This may due to two important points: (1) the absence of researches on defining designers' materials considerations and (2) translating those considerations to an objective source. This research aims to find out an answer for the first point above; that is, it addresses the designers' concerns on materials beyond technical. For this aim, the first section consists of the characteristics of materials, which are touched upon in related literature, for demarcating the intangible characteristics of materials (ICM). After that, the second section contains a part of a field study conducted with 20 industrial designers in Turkey for exploring their materials considerations and the data they need while selecting materials.

2 Intangible characteristics of materials (ICM)

Industrial designers may have several questions regarding to intangible characteristics of materials (ICM) come along with the materials selection process, like "Does the selected material support the indented meaning of the product?", "Does it convenient for the aimed target group?", or "what kinds of associations can it evoke in users' minds?".

In existing literature on materials and design, the collective approach is their emphasis on the significance of the ICM. They mention these characteristics in various ways; such as, the

second and third order materials characteristics (Hodgson and Harper, 2004), emotive- stage materials characteristics and softer criteria of materials' considerations, invisible characteristics (Lefteri, 2005), less tangible issues of materials (Conran, 2005), qualitative properties (Jee and Kang, 2001; Edwards, 2002), non-active or passive functions of materials (Deng and Edwards, 2005), non- technical issues of materials (Ferrante et al, 2000), material image, metaphysical aspects of materials, non- physical properties of materials (Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003), material personality, personal dimensions of materials (Ashby and Johnson, 2002, 2003), intrinsic cultural meanings of materials (Manzini, 1986), subjective dimensions, essential and indicative character of materials (Rognoli and Levi, 2004), perceived characteristics of materials (Zuo, 2005), and perceived values of materials (Karana, 2004a, 2004b). Although, most of the authors try to highlight the similar kinds of materials characteristics with the terms above, there is not an exact, or conjunctive, definition used by all of them. On the other hand, the one of the most important common points lying under the given terms is that they are all expressing some *intangible* characteristics.

The dictionary definition of *intangible* is: (1) not having a physical substance or intrinsic productive value (of especially business assets: intangible assets such as good will), (2) incapable of being perceived by senses especially the sense of touch, (3) hard to pin down or identify, (4) lacking substance or reality; incapable of being touched or seen (Word Net, 2005). When it is adapted to the materials domain, the *intangible characteristics of materials* contain the characteristics which cannot be perceived by senses and cannot be identified easily by people. For instance, perceived attributes of materials, associations which they evoke, and the feelings and emotions they create on user are all the ICM, based on the dictionary meaning of *intangible*. An overview of how people evaluate materials and the definition of the ICM for this study can be seen in **Figure 1**. The figure provides seven categories which are used to explain the evaluation of materials: (1) physical properties, (2) production techniques, (3) use & function, (4) sensorial properties, (5) perceptions, (6) associations and (7) emotions. Last three categories (perceptions, associations and emotions) are defined as the intangible characteristics of materials in Figure 1.

EVALUATION OF MATERIALS

Figure1: Intangible characteristics of Materials (ICM) in materials evaluation.

Although in literature, as it was affirmed in previous paragraphs, the significance of benefiting from the ICM for designers is emphasized, only few of the authors (Hodgson and Harper, 2004; Ferrante et al, 2000; Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003; Karana, 2004b; Zuo, 2005) made field studies on the subject and proposed a way for linking them to materials selection process for designers. Explicitly, there is not a materials selection source, which integrates the ICM with the tangible selection activity in the design process and the existing engineering based sources are inadequate for industrial designers (Karana, 2004a; Deng and Edwards, 2005; Hodgson and Harper, 2004; Lovatt and Shercliff, 1995; Zuo, 2005; Lefteri, 2005; Conran, 2005; Sapuan, 2001; Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003). The next section focuses on a part of the evaluations from a field study, particularly concentrating on the role of ICM in materials considerations of industrial designers.

3 Design and conduct of field study

3.1 Definition of the participants and the procedure

The specific aim for the field study was to examine what kind of data industrial designers need in order to select materials. The criteria, which would affect the designers' material selection processes and the type of data they need about materials, were defined. The foremost one of those criteria was whether the designer works as an in-house designer in a manufacturing firm or as a consultant designer to various different firms. Therefore, the sample group was including both in-house and consultant industrial designers in equal numbers.

The study was applied to 20 industrial designers in Turkey, who work professionally. The in-house designers of the sample group were selected from the firms that involve the R&D (Research and Development) departments in their body; the designers work in the same atmosphere with people from different professions and have a huge capacity of production. These were ASELSAN, VESTEL Electronic, KAREL, ARÇELİK, NURUS and MAN Türkiye.

The consultant designers of the sample group were from the firms that serve for design and consultation and do not involve the production in their body, such as Tasarım Üssü, Nesne Design, Centipede Design (kırkayak design), and Kilittaşı, Unique Projects Factory, Özden Design Ltd. Apart from those firms; the research was also implemented to two designers who are related to product design not being under the name of any firm in addition to their academic identity in universities: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Asatekin (Middle East Technical University) and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Oya Şenocak Akman (Istanbul Technical University).

Two techniques have been used to analyze the group: interviews and questionnaires. Attention was paid to conduct the interviews in designers' original working environment, in case they would like to give exact names for the sources they use for material selection in their offices. The interviews and the questionnaires were focusing on the issues of materials selection processes, materials selection sources, and the characteristics of materials about which designers would like to obtain information (or access data) while selecting materials. In this paper, a part from the whole evaluation of the field study (Karana, 2004b), basically concentrating on the last issue- that is, the materials characteristics which are crucial in selecting materials for industrial designers- was taken into account in order to emphasize the significance of the ICM.

3.2 The brief evaluation of the field study and Discussion

The findings of the field study prove that, most of the interviewed designers (18 out of 20), especially the in-house ones (all of them), can easily access the technical data about materials. However for pre- selection process, in which they make their preliminary decisions for the materials of their products, they do not use only technical data. On the contrary, the technical data comes third in list which consists of designers' priorities while searching for a material (**Table 1**).

All the interviewees emphasized that, the cultural backgrounds of the people and their past experiences with the products are effective in their products and materials preferences. In other words, people can perceive a material as more valuable than the other, and can make some associations based on their backgrounds and experiences.

Therefore, among the various alternative products with different materials of nearly equal technical qualities, people can prefer one product to another based on these issues, which were defined as *intangible characteristics of materials* previously.

Table 1 Outline for the sequence of the required data of a materials selection source for industrial designers

As it is seen in table 1, the industrial designers initially look for the data on *sensorial properties of materials* in materials selection process. They believe that the ICM are certainly important issues in their selections and the sensorial properties of materials are one of the most vital aspects of materials for creating the ICM. For instance, for attributing the meaning of ‘modern’ (which is a term expressing an intangible characteristic) to a material, they prefer to select a material providing a grey, shiny and smooth surface (which are three features representing the sensorial properties of materials). This explains why sensorial properties of materials come first in ‘content of needed data’ list in table 1. Moreover, according to interviewees, most of the Turkish industrial designers, unless the particular criteria for a material are defined at the beginning of the design project, make their preliminary selections depending on *the appearance of the materials*, that is the texture, final surface finishing, color and all the properties appealing to the sensorial evaluations.

In the concept creation period (pre- selection process), the interviewees consider the technical properties and manufacturing techniques of materials. However, they do not evaluate those factors profoundly. When they finish the conceptual period and proceed to the ‘embodiment’ and ‘detailed design’ periods, they begin to concentrate on those subjects intensively. They search for technical and mechanical properties of the material, appropriateness of it to the existing manufacturing techniques and the cost of overall production.

The Table 1 also consists of some noteworthy keywords like durability given by designers as the most effective criteria on materials selection process. As it is seen in table, the ‘availability’ factor- easy access to the selected materials- was written vertically, because the time for searching for this criterion was not defined definitely by interviewed designers, that is, ‘availability’ factor is evaluated any time through the whole stage. In fact, this is the most important factor for them and designers commence to consider it from the beginning of the process.

Another factor that does not have a defined place in the selection process is the ‘consultancy’. The interviewees stated that they need advice about materials at every

stage of the design activity. Therefore, if the contact data of any consultancy service on candidate materials can be offered, it would be very valuable for them.

Finally, there seems the 'design note' title in the 'outline'. This title includes special design limitations related with the requirements about the form creation, combined materials and health & safety regulations, recommended using environment, similar materials which can be used instead of the selected material, environmental notes like sustainability or recycle ability of the material, and some specific design notes from the experienced industrial designers.

4 Conclusion

The appropriate selection of a material for a product in industrial design does not only provide technical superiority but also the opportunity to create various intangible aspects of products, like perceptions, associations and emotions.

Intangible characteristics of materials (ICM) - involving the perceptive characteristics of materials, associations and emotions evoked by materials- are used by most of the industrial designers in order to create the intended meanings with the appropriate selections. Industrial designers usually benefit from the other properties of materials, like sensorial properties, to attain the ICM. Consequently, the researches with more emphasis on intangible characteristics of materials and the integration of these aspects of materials into materials selection sources can provide a considerable advantage for industrial design society.

References

Arabe, K C (2004) Materials' central role in product personality, *Thomas Net Industrial News Room (March)*

URL: http://news.thomasnet.com/IMT/archives/2004/03/materials_cent.html

Ashby, Mike and Johnson, Kara (2002) *Materials and Design: The Art and Science of Material Selection in Product Design*, Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford, UK

Ashby, Mike and Johnson, Kara (2003) the Art of Materials Selection, *Materials Today* (December): 24-35

Conran, S (2005), Creating Value- Keynote Address International Conference on the Art of Plastics Design, Berlin, Germany (18-19 October) paper 1

Deng, Y M and Edwards, K L (2005) The Role of materials identification and selection in engineering design, *Materials and Design*, in press.

Edwards, K L (2002) Towards more strategic product design for manufacture and assembly: priorities for concurrent engineering, *Materials and Design* (23): 651-656

Ferrante, M, Santos, S F, de Castro, J F R (2000) Materials selection as an interdisciplinary technical activity: basic methodology and case studies, *Materials Research* (Volume 3, No. 2): 1- 9

Hodgson, S N B and Harper, J F (2004) Effective use of materials in the design process- more than a selection problem, *International engineering and product design education conference*, Delft (2-3 September)

Jee, Dong- Hyun and Kang, Ki- Ju (2001) A method for optimal material selection aided with decision making theory, *Materials and Design* (Volume 21): 199-206

Karana, E (2004a) The Meaning of the Material: A Survey on the Role of Material in User's Evaluation of a Design Object, *4th International Conference on Design and Emotion*

Karana, E (2004b) *Guidelines for a Materials Selection Source for Industrial Design Activity: A survey on the Expectations of Turkish Designers* Thesis (Ms) METU, Ankara, Turkey

Lefteri, C (2005) The branding of plastics- how important is the branding of a material and how far do plastics go in helping to define brands, *International Conference on the Art of Plastics Design*, Berlin, Germany (18-19 October) paper 7

Ljungberg, L Y and Edwards, K L (2003) Design, materials selection and marketing of successful products, *Materials and Design* (24): 519-529

Lovatt, A M, Shercliff, H R (1998) Manufacturing process selection in engineering design. Part 1: the role of process selection, *Materials and Design* (19): 205- 215

Manzini, Ezio (1986) *The Material of Invention*. Arcadia srl, Milano.

Rognoli, V and Levi, M (2004) How, what and where is possible to learn design materials? , *International engineering and product design education conference*, Delft (2-3 September)

Sapuan, S M (2001) A knowledge-based system for materials selection in mechanical engineering design, *Materials and Design* (22): 687- 695

Zuo, H, Jones, M and Hope, T (2005), Material texture perception in product design, *International Conference on the Art of Plastics Design*, Berlin, Germany (18-19 October) paper 5